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Three-dimensional experimental investigation of the interaction between a rising bubble and a vortex ring

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The interaction between turbulent flows and bubbles is a complex phenomenon ubiquitous in natural and industrial settings. In this work, we experimentally investigate, from a fundamental perspective, the interaction between a rising bubble and a vortex ring in counterflow. Using time-resolved three-dimensional Lagrangian Particle Tracking (4D-LPT) coupled with shadowgraphy, we obtain simultaneous measurements of the bubble motion and the surrounding liquid flow. This approach enables detailed observation of bubble dynamics, deformation, and eventual breakup, as well as the fluid motion. We examine several flow configurations by varying the vortex circulation and the Weber number while maintaining a comparable vortex-to-bubble size ratio. Based on these measurements, we classify the interaction events into three categories according to their impact on bubble dynamics and vortex stability over time. Through experiments, we address for the first time the three-dimensional effects of these interactions, which had not been considered in previous studies. The analysed experiments comprise: Case I, corresponding to a weak interaction in which neither the bubble nor the vortex is significantly affected; Case II, where the bubble is captured and advected by the vortex, leading to a strong distortion of the vortex due to the presence of the bubble within its core; and Case III, involving a stronger vortex capable of capturing the bubble and breaking it into two fragments without a severe loss of energy in the vortex core. The analysis of these results provides insight into the bubble breakup process and the mechanisms responsible for the destabilisation of the vortex ring.

Key words: Bubble breakup, Turbulent flows, 4D-LPT, Vortex ring

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35 1. Introduction

36 Investigating the complex interactions between bubbles, inertial particles, and vortical
 37 structures present in turbulent flows is essential to understand a wide range of engineering
 38 operations and natural phenomena, including turbulent flows in chemical reactors, mixing in
 39 oceanic layers, ship hydrodynamics, and drag reduction applications (Berkman & Calabrese
 40 1988; Prince & Blanch 1990; Melville 1996; Deane & Stokes 2002; van Gils *et al.* 2013;
 41 Ferrante & Elghobashi 2004). In such systems, the presence and deformation of bubbles
 42 substantially influence the transport of mass, momentum, and energy within the continuous
 43 phase, while the turbulent flow exerts dynamic forces that dictate both bubble dynamics
 44 and the resulting size distribution. Despite their importance, the mechanisms by which the
 45 dispersed phase modulates turbulence, and how this modulation depends on key physical
 46 parameters, are poorly understood (Ruetsch & Meiburg 1994; Climent & Magnaudet 2006;
 47 Balachandar & Eaton 2010; Spandan *et al.* 2017). This knowledge gap persists largely due
 48 to the intricate, non-linear nature of these two-way interactions, making them a subject of
 49 ongoing and fundamental research (Perrard *et al.* 2021; Pandey *et al.* 2021; Rivière *et al.*
 50 2023).

51 The bubble-turbulent flow interaction could lead to bubble breakup. In particular, bubble
 52 fragmentation in turbulent flows has been extensively studied since the foundational works
 53 of Kolmogorov (1949) and Hinze (1955). These seminal studies established that bubbles
 54 or droplets break when turbulent stresses overcome surface tension forces (Martínez-Bazán
 55 *et al.* 1999*a,b*), broadly categorised into inertial mechanisms at high Weber numbers, and
 56 resonance mechanisms at low Weber numbers (Risso & Fabre 1998; Revuelta *et al.* 2006,
 57 2008). Here, the Weber number, $We = \rho \varepsilon^{2/3} R_b^{5/3} / \sigma$, is defined as the ratio between the
 58 turbulent stresses acting on the surface of the bubble, $\tau_t \sim \rho (\varepsilon R_b)^{2/3}$, and the confining
 59 stresses due to surface tension, $\tau_s \sim \sigma / R_b$, where ρ is the liquid density, σ the surface
 60 tension, ε the dissipation rate of turbulent kinetic energy per unit mass and R_b is the bubble
 61 radius. A widely accepted hypothesis from this framework, known as the Kolmogorov-Hinze
 62 (KH) paradigm, postulates that bubbles are primarily broken by turbulent eddies of similar
 63 size (Hinze 1955; Chan *et al.* 2021; Masuk *et al.* 2021; Qi *et al.* 2022). Larger eddies
 64 are believed to transport the bubble without breaking it, while smaller ones lack sufficient
 65 energy for rupture. However, testing this hypothesis has been challenging directly due to the
 66 multiscale nature of turbulence, where eddies of various sizes are present simultaneously (Qi
 67 *et al.* 2024).

68 To simplify the complexity of the interaction of bubbles and turbulent flows and gain
 69 fundamental insight, the interaction between a single bubble and a vortex ring, which serves
 70 as a model for a turbulent eddy, is an idealised scenario (Chahine 1995; Jha & Govardhan
 71 2015; Martínez-Bazán 2015). This approach provides a controlled framework to unravel
 72 the underlying mechanisms governing bubble or particle deformation dynamics and their
 73 reciprocal influence on vortex behaviour.

74 A series of experimental studies has shed light on the complex interaction between
 75 vortex rings and bubbles or particles. Sridhar & Katz (1999) reported that microbubbles
 76 could distort a vortex ring core, with the core eventually regaining its initial state after
 77 the bubbles escaped. Jha & Govardhan (2015) conducted controlled experiments in a co-
 78 current configuration by generating vortex rings and injecting air bubbles of known volume
 79 by their side, revealing a four-stage interaction process: capture, azimuthal elongation and
 80 gradual breakup, post-breakup motion, and eventual escape. Their work highlighted that
 81 bubbles could significantly distort vortex rings, particularly at low Weber numbers, exhibiting
 82 similarities with phenomena observed in turbulent bubbly flows, such as enstrophy reduction
 83 and distortion of structures. Zednikova *et al.* (2019) experimentally investigated bubble

84 breakup triggered by vortex ring impact, establishing this interaction as a deterministic
85 alternative to the stochastic nature of bubble fragmentation in turbulent flows. They quantified
86 breakup frequency, the mean number of daughter bubbles, and size distributions using high-
87 speed imaging. Building on this work, Biswas & Govardhan (2022) carried out a series
88 of experiments emphasising the role of deformability and size. A comparison between a
89 deformable air bubble and a rigid buoyant particle demonstrated that bubble deformability
90 fundamentally alters the interaction dynamics from the capture phase onward, with rigid
91 particles causing a stronger disruption of the vortex structure. Moreover, the same authors
92 focused on the bubble-to-vortex-core size ratio, finding that larger ratios at low We induce
93 stronger vortex core deformation and fragmentation, leading to marked reductions in both
94 convection speed and azimuthal enstrophy (Biswas & Govardhan 2023) (hereafter, the
95 contribution of the azimuthal vorticity to the enstrophy, defined in equation 2.2, will referred
96 to as the azimuthal enstrophy, Ω_θ). They identified a scaling law for these reductions
97 and analysed bubble elongation, breakup modes, and cascade breakup time. Most recently,
98 Biswas & Govardhan (2025) extended their analysis to rigid particles interacting with vortex
99 rings while varying the particle-to-core size ratio. Results confirmed that larger particles
100 significantly disrupt vortex dynamics, with effects more pronounced than those observed for
101 deformable bubbles.

102 Nevertheless, most of these experimental studies rely on two-dimensional measurements
103 or partial data. In this regard, numerical studies can complement them by providing detailed
104 three-dimensional insight into flow fields and grant access to parameters that are challenging
105 to measure experimentally. Early numerical studies by Higuera (2004) and Revuelta (2010)
106 explored the axisymmetric interaction of an inviscid vortex ring with a bubble, revealing
107 different breakup modes depending on the vortex-to-bubble size ratio and Weber number.
108 These studies primarily focused on bubble deformation and breakup occurring outside the
109 vortex core. Other numerical investigations, such as those by Chahine (1995) and Ferrante
110 & Elghobashi (2007), explored scenarios where bubbles were entrained into vortex cores,
111 observing extreme elongation, wrapping, and reduction of vorticity and enstrophy. Foronda-
112 Trillo *et al.* (2021) carried out fully three-dimensional simulations, systematically varying
113 We and the vortex-to-bubble size ratio. Their results, supported by experimental validation,
114 revealed similar qualitative behaviour but suggested that the bubble presence does not
115 significantly affect the global vortex enstrophy. Instead, they observed a redistribution of
116 the enstrophy from the azimuthal to the radial and axial components following the loss of
117 axial symmetry. They also highlighted that the sensitivity to initial conditions can lead to a
118 probabilistic nature of bubble breakup, even in nominally deterministic systems. Similarly,
119 Cihonski *et al.* (2013) showed that the reaction forces exerted by bubbles on the fluid,
120 under traditional two-way coupling assumptions, may be too small to significantly distort
121 the vortex core. More recently, New *et al.* (2024) used large-eddy simulations (LES) to
122 study vortex ring collisions with hemispherical solids. Although focused on rigid bodies,
123 their work provides valuable insight into the three-dimensional vortex dynamics and the
124 formation of secondary and tertiary vortex structures during complex interactions. Together,
125 these numerical studies demonstrate that high-fidelity simulations are essential to capture
126 the fine-scale features of bubble–vortex and particle–vortex interactions, particularly those
127 that elude direct measurement. However, while numerical simulations provide a powerful
128 theoretical framework, their inherent simplifications require the use of three-dimensional
129 experimental techniques.

130 Despite significant progress in understanding this problem, several key questions remain
131 open. For instance, the exact mechanisms of turbulence modulation by bubbles, as well
132 as their parametric dependence, are still not fully understood (Jha & Govardhan 2015;
133 Biswas & Govardhan 2022). Furthermore, the precise origins of vortex instabilities and

134 core fragmentation at low We , and their role in the observed reduction of convection speed,
 135 remain unclear (Jha & Govardhan 2015; Martínez-Bazán 2015). Discrepancies between
 136 experimental and numerical results regarding the redistribution of vorticity, enstrophy, and
 137 circulation also persist. Finally, the optimal vortex-to-bubble size ratio and the influence of the
 138 vortex core-to-vortex radius ratio (a_0/R_0) on breakup efficiency require further investigation,
 139 particularly in relation to the observed minimum critical Weber number (Foronda-Trillo *et al.*
 140 2021).

141 Thus, the current work aims to address these open questions by providing a comprehensive,
 142 three-dimensional characterisation of bubble-vortex interaction dynamics. This work will
 143 experimentally characterise the dynamics of the interaction of a bubble with a vortex
 144 ring using advanced time-resolved 4D-LPT coupled with shadowgraphy. This experimental
 145 technique allows for detailed three-dimensional flow field measurements along with three-
 146 dimensional measurements of the bubble's motion, as well as the intricate fluid behaviour
 147 within the vortex. In this way, we can address the existing discrepancies in literature and
 148 unravel existing challenges, such as (i) the true three-dimensional evolution of vorticity and
 149 enstrophy during the interaction, allowing for definitive conclusions on whether vorticity is
 150 redistributed or dissipated; (ii) the complex three-dimensional nature of vortex instabilities
 151 and their development in the presence of a bubble; (iii) the coupling between bubble
 152 deformation and the three-dimensional flow field changes within the vortex core.

153 The work is organised as follows. Section 2 clarifies the experimental methodology. The
 154 experimental facility is described in Section 2.1, where we present the problem and the
 155 relevant variables, as well as the parameter ranges considered. Sections 2.2 and 2.3 detail
 156 how the data were obtained and the techniques used to analyse the flow and bubble dynamics,
 157 respectively, while the vortex identification algorithm is described in Section 2.4. Section 3
 158 presents the results: first, the different types of interaction explored in this study are outlined
 159 in Section 3.1, followed by Sections 3.2 to 3.4, which describe the behaviour of Cases I to
 160 III, respectively. Finally, Section 4 presents the conclusions and discussion of the results.

161 2. Methodology

162

2.1. Description of the experiment

163 We consider a simplified configuration (see figure 1) involving a single bubble of equivalent
 164 radius R_b , density ρ_g , kinematic viscosity ν_g and surface tension σ , rising in a still liquid
 165 with known density and kinematic viscosity, ρ and ν , respectively. When rising along the
 166 vertical direction (against gravity), the bubble interacts with a downwards-directed vortex
 167 ring of radius $R(t)$, core radius $a(t)$, and circulation $\Gamma(t)$, with their initial values denoted
 168 as R_0 , a_0 , and Γ_0 (see figure 1a). These variables are obtained at $t = t_0$, when the vortex has
 169 completely entered the measurement volume. Here, $t_0 < 0$ since we define $t = 0$ as the time
 170 when the bubble begins to interact with the vortex ring. The non-dimensional quantities are
 171 then computed using, R_0 , R_0^2/Γ_0 and Γ_0/R_0 , as the characteristic length, time, and velocity,
 172 respectively. Note that we define the dimensionless circulation as $\Gamma_0/(U_0R_0)$, based on the
 173 theoretical model for a Lamb-Oseen vortex ring, $U_0R_0 = \Gamma_0/(4\pi)[\ln(8R_0/a_0) - 1/4]$ (Lamb
 174 1924).

175 To describe the vortex-bubble interaction, two coordinate systems are used: a Cartesian
 176 system in which y is the vertical direction and x, z are the horizontal coordinates, and a
 177 cylindrical one in which the radial coordinate is $r = \sqrt{x^2 + z^2}$ and the azimuthal coordinate
 178 is θ , with y the vertical one (see figure 1). Figure 1(b) shows a top view of the bubble-
 179 vortex interaction. Here, θ_{bubble} defines the range of azimuthal planes covered by the bubble
 180 (shaded area in figure 1b). Note that this value is affected by the bubble shape but also by

Figure 1: (a) Three-dimensional sketch of the problem with the main involved variables and reference frames. (b) Top-view showing the azimuthal sector covered by the bubble (θ_{bubble} , grey area) before (top) and during (bottom) the interaction.

181 its radial position: when the bubble is released ($t < 0$, figure 1b top), it is nearly centred in
 182 the vertical axis and $\theta_{bubble} \approx 360^\circ$, but when the interaction takes place, the bubble moves
 183 radially towards the vortex core and, therefore, θ_{bubble} decreases.

184 Since $\rho \gg \rho_g$ and $\nu \gg \nu_g$, the vortex-bubble interaction can be described in terms of
 185 four dimensionless numbers: the Weber number, $We = \rho (\Gamma_0/2\pi R_0)^2/(\sigma/R_b)$, Reynolds
 186 number, $Re = \Gamma_0/\nu$, vortex-to-bubble size ratio (R_0/R_b), and core-to-vortex ring radius ratio
 187 (a_0/R_0). The bubble motion prior to its interaction with the vortex can be characterised in
 188 terms of the Bond, $Bo = \rho g R_b^2/\sigma$, and Galilei, $Ga = \sqrt{g R_b} R_b/\nu$, numbers.

189 The experiments were carried out at the Institute of Fluid Mechanics of Toulouse (IMFT).
 190 The experimental facility consisted of a $0.25 \times 0.25 \times 0.6 \text{ m}^3$ tank filled with distilled water,
 191 seeded with $56 \mu\text{m}$ polyamide particles covered with rhodamine 6G (see figure 2). Tank
 192 temperature was maintained equal to 20°C in order to keep constant water density, viscosity
 193 and refractive index. The vortex ring was generated by injecting a transient water jet from
 194 a pressurised reservoir into the still water tank. The jet orifice was located at the end of a
 195 200 mm long, 30 mm inner diameter rigid tube and submerged well below the water free
 196 surface to ensure a well-controlled formation process (Gharib *et al.* 1998). It was aligned
 197 with the air inlet so that the collision of the bubble and the vortex ring was forced head-on.
 198 The jet, also seeded with fluorescent particles, was controlled by means of a solenoid valve,
 199 whose opening and closure times could be remotely adjusted. The circulation of the vortex
 200 ring was controlled using a 10 mm diameter orifice, with injection pressures between 1.5
 201 and 3 bar and valve opening times ranging from 30 to 100 ms, yielding Reynolds numbers
 202 of $8 \times 10^3 \lesssim Re \lesssim 15 \times 10^3$ and core-to-vortex radii ratios $a_0/R_0 \approx 0.3$ to 0.4.

203 The bubble was released from the bottom using a syringe, a conical nozzle and a very

Figure 2: (a) Isometric and (b) frontal view of experimental facility. Cameras used for recording the field of view are numbered 1 to 6 in (a).

204 low flow rate. The nozzle diameter was adjusted depending on the desired bubble volume
 205 to guarantee the expected vortex-to-bubble size ratio, $R_0/R_b \approx 4.5$. The air nozzle diameter
 206 was 5.5 mm, yielding bubble radii R_b of 3.65 ± 0.05 mm. This parameter combination led
 207 to $R_0/R_b \approx 4.5$, providing $0.4 \lesssim We \lesssim 1$, $1.6 \lesssim Bo \lesssim 1.8$, and $615 \lesssim Ga \lesssim 690$. Upon
 208 release, the bubble would activate a photodiode sensor whose signal would then trigger the
 209 recording, as well as open the valve after a user-preset delay. Thanks to the repeatability of
 210 the experiment, the delay was adjusted so that most of the interaction between the bubble
 211 and the vortex ring happened within the field of view of all cameras.

212 The experiments were recorded at 1496 Hz acquisition frequency, using six high speed
 213 cameras: four VEO640L Phantom cameras from Vision Research[®] (2560×1600 pixels)
 214 equipped with 200 mm F/16 Nikon lenses placed on a bench 100 cm away from the frontal
 215 face of the tank (cameras 1-4 in figure 2a, shown also in the frontal view in figure 2b); and
 216 two PCO DIMAX HS4 (2016 × 2016 pixels windowed to 1632 × 2016 pixels) equipped
 217 with 100 mm F/16 Nikon lenses located at one rear corner of the tank for a lateral view
 218 (cameras 5 and 6 in figure 2a). Details on how the images obtained from these 6 cameras
 219 were calibrated may be found in Appendix A. To avoid reflections from the laser beam
 220 on the complex bubble interface and highlight the light scattering in the fluorescent seeding
 221 particles, the camera lenses were equipped with optical high-pass filters (540 nm). The camera
 222 setup provided multiple points of view, which optimised the tomographic measurements. A
 223 two-angle manual Scheimpflug mount was used between the lens and the sensor of each
 224 camera to compensate for the angular positioning required by the setup, ensuring minimal
 225 image distortion. In this manner, the horizontal angles between the optical axes of the frontal
 226 cameras 1-2 and 3-4 were $40^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. The vertical angles of the cameras 1-3, 2-4 and 5-6
 227 were also $40^\circ \pm 1^\circ$, and the horizontal angles between the optical axes of the frontal and side
 228 cameras 2-6 and 4-5 were $97^\circ \pm 1^\circ$. Two LED backlight sources were also included to obtain
 229 the bubble deformations and the eventual bubble breakup process via shadowgraphy. The
 230 illumination for the 4D-LPT images was provided by a 527 nm, 60 mJ/pulse double-pulsed
 231 laser (Photonics[®], ref. DM60-527-DH) together with a volumetric illumination optics lens
 232 from LaVision GmbH, generating an expanded and collimated laser beam. The latter was
 233 filtered by a set of knife-edge panels, providing a $100 \times 160 \times 80$ mm³ ($L_x \times L_y \times L_z$)
 234 field of view (figure 2b). This measurement volume was located at mid-height of the tank to
 235 ensure that, when reaching it, the vortex ring was already properly formed and the bubble had

236 reached its quasi-terminal rise path and velocity. However, it was placed closer to the front
237 wall of the tank (~ 40 mm distance) to minimise turbidity caused by the particles present
238 between the measuring volume and the wall, thus optimising optical access for the 4 front
239 cameras, yet at a distance sufficient to avoid wall effects ($\sim 4R_0 \approx 18R_b$). An additional
240 high-speed camera (see figure 2a) was placed near the injection point of the bubble to record
241 the bubble formation and pinch-off process. This allowed us to corroborate that the formation
242 was quasi-static and to have a precise estimation of the bubble volume from the frame taken
243 right after release, when the bubble was still axisymmetric. The images from this camera
244 were calibrated using a 1 mm precision scale.

245

2.2. Characterization of the flow field: 4D-LPT

246 The liquid velocity field was characterised using 4D Lagrangian Particle Tracking (4D-
247 LPT), a laser velocimetry technique based on the Shake-The-Box algorithm implemented
248 in the DaVis LaVision software, which allowed us to reconstruct three-dimensional tracer
249 particle trajectories over time, providing volumetric velocity fields and enabling the analysis
250 of complex, unsteady flow structures.

251 The Shake-The-Box (STB) technique (Schanz *et al.* 2016) was employed to capture the
252 evolution of the flow field using the four frontal cameras. The results using six cameras were
253 similar qualitatively, but fewer particles could be tracked as the thickness of the measurement
254 volume seen by the two lateral cameras is larger than their depth of field, the image quality
255 being thus affected by the amount of out-of-focus highlighted particles. Once we performed
256 an accurate calibration of the 4 frontal cameras (see Appendix A), the STB technique is
257 able to determine the trajectories of the particles resolved in time in 3D at very high particle
258 densities, greater than 0.05 particles per pixel (Schanz *et al.* 2013, 2016). This is possible
259 because of the predictive nature of this algorithm, which uses the information of existing
260 particle tracks to anticipate the most probable optical solution for the following time step
261 instead of reconstructing the whole volume, thus reducing ghost particles and computational
262 resources (Schanz *et al.* 2016; Lorite-Díez *et al.* 2022). This initial guess is then refined to
263 match the recorded images.

264 In our experiments, the images were preprocessed to maximise the contrast between the
265 particles and the background. However, to avoid possible disturbances due to reflections, a
266 threshold was set on image intensity, so that only pixels above 12-20% of the maximum
267 intensity were considered as possible particles. Additionally, velocity and acceleration
268 thresholds were manually set according to the apparent maximum displacement of the
269 particles in the area of interest (the maximum velocities were expected at the centre of
270 the ring and at the cores) and were then adjusted after several iterations so that the maximum
271 velocity could be captured with the minimum particle identification errors. To further refine
272 the reconstruction of the paths, we set a minimum track length of 5 time steps to neglect any
273 possible ghost particles, and included several iterations where we gradually decreased the
274 temporal increment (from 6 to 1 time step), alternating passes both forward and backwards in
275 time, while reconnecting interrupted paths between passes. With this method and an allowed
276 search volume of 1.5 voxels, we achieved around 80 to 100 thousand tracks, depending on the
277 specific seeding conditions in each experiment. The velocities of the particles were derived
278 by fitting the trajectories with a polynomial of order 3 to compute the tracks for each time
279 step, considering a time window of 15 steps. Finally, the Lagrangian trajectory data were
280 converted to an Eulerian grid, providing cubic sub-volumes containing a number of particles
281 representative enough so that the resulting vectors could describe the fluid motion accurately
282 (typical grid size between 13 and 18 voxels, implying a resolution between 0.7 and 1 mm).

Figure 3: Left: snapshots of a broken bubble, as viewed from each camera: (a) raw images, (b) preprocessed images, (c) isolated objects. Right: volumetric reconstruction of the bubble, (d) yz view, (e) xz view. A supplementary movie related to this figure (Movie1_reconstruction.mp4) is accessible at journals.cambridge.org.

283

2.3. Bubble shape and motion: tomographic reconstruction

284 To analyse the bubble dynamics, the shadow projections of the bubble on each camera were
 285 isolated from the greyscale images of the six cameras (figure 3a) by means of a segmentation
 286 procedure similar to that by Boulesteix (2010). Firstly, the background was calculated by
 287 means of a median filter, and the image was divided over the background to enhance the
 288 contrast of the bubble (see figure 3b). Then, a hysteresis threshold was applied to the gradient
 289 image and the contour of the bubble was isolated by finding the local maxima in the gradient
 290 image in the direction perpendicular to the gradient. Finally, the remaining open contours
 291 were closed by filling the image in the direction of the gradient and using consecutive dilation
 292 and erosion operations. The isolated bubbles are shown in figure 3(c).

293 The commercial software DaVis 11 from LaVision GmbH was used to reconstruct a three-
 294 dimensional volume using the six available bubble projections and an accurate 3D calibration
 295 (see Appendix A). The camera arrangement was essential for the quality of the tomographic
 296 reconstruction. On the one hand, the small angles between each pair of front cameras allow
 297 for an accurate determination of the position of the bubbles in a vertical plane. On the other
 298 hand, the large angles between the front and lateral cameras provide a variety of points of
 299 view, which helps to constrain the reconstruction, avoiding the distortion of the volume due
 300 to a lack of depth perception (Tödter *et al.* 2025).

301 The Multiplicative Line-Of-Sight (MLOS) reconstruction technique was used for the
 302 reconstruction of the bubble. The resulting objects, shown in figure 3(d), (e), were then
 303 corrected by eliminating the potential ghost volumes in the areas covered by the bubbles in the
 304 lines of sight of the cameras. After the objects were reconstructed, the volumes, trajectories,
 305 and velocities of the bubbles could be obtained. Excellent agreement was obtained between
 306 the reconstructed bubble volume and the axisymmetric volume inferred from the additional
 307 camera images at the end of the bubble formation process, even in the presence of bubble
 308 breakup events.

309

2.4. Data processing

310 The procedure followed to extract the vortex ring characteristics from the 3D velocity field
 311 is sketched in figure 4, and is described as follows. The first stage was to locate the vortex
 312 ring within the 3D velocity field for each time step. Our approach was to deal with the
 313 3D data as a set of consecutive 2D planes and to apply vortex identification algorithms

Figure 4: Block diagram of the post-processing routine used to locate the vortex, calculate its size and compute all its characteristic variables. In (c), Γ_1 is a scalar function used to identify the vortex ring. S is a rectangular domain of fixed size and geometry, centred in P , and N is the number of points M inside S . PM is the vector between P and each of the points M in the grid, and U_M is the velocity vector at M .

314 for 2D-PIV data that are available in the literature. To do this, we would sweep along one
 315 of the horizontal directions (e.g. z) and obtain consecutive planar velocity fields (one xy
 316 plane at every z coordinate of the 3D grid), see figure 4(a). On each individual plane, we
 317 applied a set of dimensionless integral functions proposed by Pawlak *et al.* (2007) to identify
 318 the vortex position. From the integration of the radial velocity along the axial coordinate
 319 (see equation (7) in Pawlak *et al.* 2007), we obtain the vertical position of the two vortex
 320 cores present in each plane (y_{cl} , y_{cr} , where cl stands for left core and cr , for right core).
 321 Equation (9) in Pawlak *et al.* (2007), responsive to variations in the momentum fluxes
 322 across the surface of a cylinder aligned with the y axis, was applied at y_{cl} and y_{cr} , giving
 323 their horizontal coordinates (e.g. x_{cl} , x_{cr}). The diameter of the vortex was calculated as the
 324 distance between the cores: $d_z = \sqrt{(y_{cl} - y_{cr})^2 + (x_{cl} - x_{cr})^2}$. The plane where the diameter
 325 of the vortex was maximum marked the coordinate of the centre of the vortex ring in such
 326 direction, z_v . The same procedure was repeated for the remaining horizontal direction (e.g.
 327 sweep along x to find x_v). The crossing point between the central planes (x_v , z_v) will define
 328 the centre of the vortex at each time step (see figure 4a), along with the vertical coordinate,
 329 y_v , defined as the average of the vertical positions of the cores at the central plane in each

330 direction $(y_{cl_x}, y_{cr_x}, y_{cl_z}, y_{cr_z})$. The difference between these vertical coordinates was
 331 generally under 2 mm.

332 The next step was to compute a polar transformation of the coordinates to capture the
 333 cylindrical-symmetric nature of the problem, namely $(x, z, y) \rightarrow (r, \theta, y)$. Note that the
 334 origin of the reference frame was located at $(x_{v_0}, z_{v_0}, y_{v_0})$, i.e., the coordinates of the vortex
 335 ring centre at the initial time step, $t = t_0$. Similarly to the previous procedure, the volume
 336 was sectioned, but this time, azimuthally, i.e., we selected one yr plane for each θ value, and
 337 each division was analysed individually in 2D. At first approach, these vertical planes cover
 338 both cores and thus θ will vary between 0 and 180° (full planes hereinafter). The volume was
 339 sectioned into 80 divisions containing two cores, thus providing 160 sections (half-planes
 340 hereinafter) where the behaviour of the vortex ring core could be analysed. Therefore, each
 341 one of the 80 planes yields a planar velocity field, similar to those obtained by 2D-PIV
 342 measurements. In this way, for an ideal, unperturbed vortex ring, the information in all the
 343 divisions would be the same: two cores of radius a separated horizontally by a distance $2R$
 344 (see figure 4b). Nevertheless, this picture is expected to change in the presence of a bubble
 345 interacting with the vortex ring. By analysing several θ positions instead of a fixed one, this
 346 approach allows us to define the precise circular sectors where the bubble is present (θ_{bubble}
 347 in figure 1b) and whether the effect of the interaction is local at θ_{bubble} , it moves azimuthally
 348 with the bubble, or it spreads around θ within the vortex core. This is one of the advantages
 349 of using tomographic flow diagnostics, which is not achievable with 2D-PIV.

350 Once we have the azimuthal cuts of the flow field, the precise vortex core centres are
 351 identified and located based on a scalar function, Γ_1 , which was derived from the topology of
 352 the velocity field (see Eqs. 8 and 9 in Graftieaux *et al.* 2001). When applied on a yr plane, the
 353 function provided peaks at the vortex cores present on such plane (see figure 4c), from where
 354 the coordinates of each peak could be obtained (y_{cl}, r_{cl} on the left, and y_{cr}, r_{cr} on the right).
 355 The differences between the radial coordinate of the centre of the vortex and its cores give
 356 us the vortex radius at each azimuthal position: $r(\theta) = r_{cr} - r_v$, $r(\theta + 180^\circ) = r_{cl} - r_v$, with
 357 $r_v = \sqrt{x_v^2 + z_v^2}$ (see black dashed lines in figure 4d). Note that r_v indicates the instantaneous
 358 radial position of the centre of the vortex, which may deviate from the y -axis.

359 Having determined the position of the vortex cores in each θ -plane, we may also compute
 360 their size. Within the azimuthal planar domain, we analysed the vertical velocity profile on a
 361 horizontal line crossing each core: $u_y(y_{cl}, r_l)$, with r_l the radial domain of the left half-plane,
 362 resp. $u_y(y_{cr}, r_r)$ for the right side. These profiles exhibit a positive and a negative peak at
 363 the outer and inner end of the core, respectively (Sullivan *et al.* 1973; Leweke & Williamson
 364 1998), as shown in figure 4(d), where the red line is the velocity profile on the right core, and
 365 the blue line is the one on the left core. The radial distance between such peaks provided the
 366 core diameter, $2a$.

367 After characterising the position and size of the vortex, we may calculate the different
 368 flow variables involved in the problem. In particular, the circulation of the vortex ring was
 369 computed by performing a surface integral of the vorticity in an enlarged area enclosing each
 370 core (left/right) of the vortex. Each area was defined as a vertical plane extending the full
 371 vertical length of the grid with a radial length covering the entire domain in the positive radial
 372 direction from r_v (i.e., r_l or r_r , respectively). Therefore, these areas constitute half-planes
 373 which are defined at each value of θ . As verification, we also computed the circulation using
 374 a line integral of the axial velocity around the boundary of the above-mentioned area. Given
 375 the Stokes theorem, both methods are equivalent (Batchelor 2000), and they gave the same
 376 results in our experiments when computed as:

$$377 \quad \Gamma(t, \theta) = \int_{\Sigma} \vec{\omega} \cdot \vec{n} \, d\sigma = \oint \vec{u} \cdot d\vec{l}, \quad (2.1)$$

378 where \vec{u} and $\vec{\omega}$ are the velocity and vorticity of the flow, \vec{n} the vector normal to the plane of
 379 surface Σ , bounded by $d\vec{l}$.

380 The vortex ring may be further analysed by calculating the kinetic energy and the enstrophy
 381 of the flow. These three-dimensional (i.e., volumetric) scalar fields are defined as follows:

$$382 \quad E_k(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_V \rho |\vec{u}|^2 dV, \\ \Omega(t) = \frac{1}{2} \int_V |\vec{\omega}|^2 dV = \frac{1}{2} \int_V (\omega_r^2 + \omega_\theta^2 + \omega_y^2) dV = \Omega_r + \Omega_\theta + \Omega_y, \quad (2.2)$$

383 where V is the volume of liquid, and Ω_r , Ω_θ , Ω_y are the contributions to the enstrophy of the
 384 radial, azimuthal, and vertical components of vorticity (ω_r , ω_θ , ω_y), respectively. We may
 385 directly adapt these three-dimensional definitions to our cartesian-grid-like domain with

$$386 \quad E_{k,V}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \rho \sum_{i=1}^{n_V} |\vec{u}_i|^2 V_i, \quad \Omega_{j,V}(t) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_V} (\omega_j)_i^2 V_i, \quad (2.3)$$

387 where \vec{u}_i and $\vec{\omega}_i$ indicate the velocity and vorticity at voxel i , respectively, n_V is the number
 388 of cells in the part of the grid considered as the integration box, V_i is the volume of the cell
 389 i in the grid, and j represents each contribution of the vorticity in the three-dimensional
 390 field (radial, azimuthal or axial). We did not take into account the whole grid, but only a
 391 reduced volume (highlighted in figure 4b), to avoid adding noise to the results. To select
 392 the optimal grid size, we performed a sensitivity analysis of its effect on the energy and
 393 enstrophy calculation. Given the cylindrical symmetry of the problem, we calculated both
 394 3D variables in several cylindrical volumetric domains of growing radius around the vortex
 395 centre. We selected the cells inside a cylinder around the vortex whose radius was as small
 396 as possible, but sufficiently large to avoid critical loss of information. Note that only the cells
 397 corresponding to the liquid were taken into account in this calculation, masking out the cells
 398 covered by the 3D-reconstructed bubble.

399

400 To be able to compare our results with the 2D studies available in the literature, we
 401 may also compute the planar kinetic energy and the planar (azimuthal) enstrophy contained
 402 within every angular division of the flow field. This will also be of interest to analyse the
 403 azimuthal region near the bubble, θ_{bubble} (see figure 1a), separately from the unperturbed
 404 zones of the vortex, thus isolating its impact more clearly. Furthermore, since the bubbles
 405 move before, during and after the interaction with the vortex ring, this approach will
 406 provide all the flow information around the bubble region, regardless of the potential bubble
 407 azimuthal displacement, in contrast with fixed-plane 2D analyses. Note that depending on the
 408 information we want to extract, we may need to analyse only half a plane (θ , to see the local
 409 effect of the bubble at the core) or gather the results from a complete azimuthal cut of the
 410 grid (θ and $\theta + 180^\circ$, e.g. to compare with typical 2D-PIV results). For this reason, although
 411 we sweep the grid for θ varying between 0 and 180° (full plane), we collect the results
 412 separately for each half-plane (θ between 0 and 360°), being our planar equations defined on
 413 a 2D domain that covers all values of y , but only r contained within the area corresponding
 414 to a vertical cut of the equivalent volumetric domain used for the 3D calculations in the same
 415 experiment. Thus, we define the planar counterparts of equation (2.3) as

$$416 \quad E_{k,A}(t, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \rho \sum_{i=1}^{n_A} |\vec{u}_{ry}|_i^2 \Delta r \Delta y, \quad \Omega_{j,A}(t, \theta) = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{i=1}^{n_A} (\omega_j)_i^2 \Delta r \Delta y, \quad (2.4)$$

417 where n_A represents the number of cells in the reduced area of the plane considered, $|\vec{u}_{r,y}|_i =$
 418 $\sqrt{u_{r,i}^2 + u_{y,i}^2}$ and $(\omega_j)_i$ are the in-plane velocity of the flow and its j -component of the
 419 vorticity at cell i in the grid, respectively, and Δr and Δy are the grid cell size in the radial
 420 and vertical directions. Notice that, although in 2D-PIV experiments only the component
 421 perpendicular to the laser plane can be obtained (typically ω_θ), we have included the three
 422 components in equation (2.4), ω_j with $j = r, \theta, y$, since all of them can be extracted in a
 423 plane from the 3D measurements.

424 To directly compare the values of the volumetric flow variables and their planar coun-
 425 terparts, we averaged them over such an area or volume. Thus, the kinetic energy and
 426 contribution of the $-j$ - component of the vorticity to the enstrophy, averaged in a plane of
 427 area $A = n_A \Delta r \Delta y$ with orientation θ at time t , referred to as specific kinetic energy and
 428 enstrophy, respectively, write

$$429 \quad E_{k,A}^s(t, \theta) = \frac{1}{n_A \Delta r \Delta y} E_{k,A}(t, \theta), \quad \Omega_{j,A}^s(t, \theta) = \frac{1}{n_A \Delta r \Delta y} \Omega_{j,A}(t, \theta). \quad (2.5)$$

430 Similarly, the specific kinetic energy and the contribution of the j -component of the vorticity
 431 to the enstrophy in a volume $V = n_V V_i$ at time t can be calculated as

$$432 \quad E_{k,V}^s(t) = \frac{1}{n_V V_i} E_{k,V}(t), \quad \Omega_{j,V}^s(t) = \frac{1}{n_V V_i} \Omega_{j,V}(t), \quad (2.6)$$

433 with $E_{k,V}(t)$ and $\Omega_{j,V}(t)$ defined in equations (2.3), being all cells of equal size. Note that
 434 for the calculation of the planar kinetic energy and enstrophy, to be coherent with their 3D
 435 counterparts, a reduced area was used instead of the full planar grid, equivalent to a planar
 436 cut of the cylindrical subvolume used in the volumetric case (see figure 4b). The decision
 437 of considering only the central region of the grid, where most of the vorticity and velocity
 438 is concentrated, for the surface/volumetric integration of these variables is essential to avoid
 439 underestimating the averaged values.

440 3. Results

441 We performed numerous experiments varying the vortex orifice diameter, the injection
 442 pressure and the valve aperture times to explore vortices with different thickness ratios and
 443 Reynolds numbers. Several bubble sizes were also used to test a wide range of vortex-to-
 444 bubble size ratios and Weber numbers. Additionally, as means of validation of our vortex
 445 identification algorithm, we completed several experiments with a vortex ring only, with no
 446 bubble interaction. However, in this work, we will focus on the details of three interaction
 447 cases, representative of the most typical behaviours found within our experiments.

448 3.1. Description of the interactions explored

449 To evaluate the three-dimensional experimental approach, we focus on three specific bubble-
 450 vortex interaction cases: Case I, in which a weak interaction between the bubble and the
 451 vortex ring takes place; Case II where the bubble is captured and dragged by the vortex; and
 452 Case III with the bubble breaking up. The three cases studied are included in figure 5, which
 453 reproduces the transition map from Foronda-Trillo *et al.* (2021). In that study, numerical
 454 simulations were performed on bubble-vortex interactions at a fixed $Re = 15000$ and a
 455 core ratio of $a_0/R_0 = 0.1$ (thin vortex rings), while experiments were performed at $Re \in$
 456 $(9000, 20000)$. The figure illustrates the breakup efficiency of experiments (hollow symbols)
 457 and numerical simulations (solid symbols), and transition curves are obtained depending on
 458 breakup probability. The three cases under study here are located in the transition region,

Figure 5: Map of the regions where bubble breakage is observed in the R_0/R_b - We plane (Foronda-Trillo *et al.* 2021). Experimental data are represented by hollow symbols indicating the bubble breakup probability. Solid symbols indicate the numerical simulations, with each symbol consisting of at least ten different simulations varying the initial position of the bubble with respect to the vortex. The solid lines separate three regions where bubbles break in all the cases, in none or only in a fraction of them. The three interaction cases studied here are highlighted in red.

Case	Description	R_0/R_b	a_0/R_0	a_0/R_b	Re	We	Bo	Ga
I	Weak interaction	4.3	0.37	1.59	8900	0.41	1.57	618.5
II	Capture, drag and release	4.5	0.38	1.71	14600	1.00	1.81	690.5
III	Bubble breakup	4.2	0.28	1.18	11800	0.77	1.75	671.5

Table 1: Dimensionless parameters describing the different types of interactions studied.

459 where eventual bubble breakup is not a deterministic phenomenon. Therefore, rather than
 460 discussing the influence of parameters on the observed dynamics, we take an experimental
 461 approach to characterise the unsteady and three-dimensional features of the three different
 462 types of interaction selected. Figure 6 depicts raw images captured at various time instants
 463 for each case. Both the bubble and the vortex ring can be observed in the figure: the bubble
 464 rises and the vortex ring descends until they interact. The type of interaction results from the
 465 values of the governing parameters, listed for each case in Table 1. Additionally, the initial
 466 characteristics of the vortex rings are detailed in Table 2.

467 Figure 6(a) shows a weak bubble-vortex interaction (Case I). As both the bubble and vortex
 468 ring come into proximity, the bubble trajectory is slightly diverted by the flow induced by
 469 the vortex. Since We is well below unity, surface tension forces dominate over the inertial
 470 forces induced by the vortex. In configurations where the vortex ring is relatively larger
 471 than the bubble ($R_0/R_b = 4.3$), interaction events at such low Weber numbers are typically
 472 characterised as “Free Crossing” events, where the bubble is not successfully trapped or
 473 broken by the vortex core (Foronda-Trillo *et al.* 2021). Thus, the flow cannot produce a
 474 sustained stretching strong enough to deform nor break the bubble. Under these conditions,
 475 the bubble undergoes only moderate, reversible deformation. Moreover, the relatively thick
 476 vortex core ($a_0/R_0 = 0.37$) presents a smoother velocity distribution than thinner vortex
 477 rings. This further reduces the ability of the vortex to hold the bubble within its core. Thus,

Figure 6: Time sequence of the front view images (camera 1) showing representative cases of three different types of interaction covered in this work. (a) Case I: Weak interaction; (b) Case II: Capture, drag and release of the bubble by the vortex ring; (c) Case III: Binary bubble breakup. Supplementary movies related to this figure (Movie2_raw_caseI.mp4, Movie3_raw_caseII.mp4, and Movie4_raw_caseIII.mp4) are accessible at journals.cambridge.org.

Case	R_0 (mm)	a_0 (mm)	Γ_0 (cm ² /s)	$\Omega_{V,0}^s$ (s ⁻²)	$E_{k,v,0}^s$ (J/m ³)
I	15.9	5.89	94.1	222.8	2.68
II	16.6	6.32	145.6	326.7	5.60
III	15.2	4.34	118.6	533.4	5.87

Table 2: Characteristic values of the vortex ring variables at $t = t_0$ for each case.

478 the bubble is accelerated towards the vortex core and reduces its rise velocity, but is not
 479 captured. After this, the bubble continues its rise upwards, restoring its path and terminal
 480 velocity after a short transient. In Case II, the interaction is more intense, as illustrated in
 481 figure 6(b), because both We and Re numbers are larger than in the previous case, while the
 482 values of the rest of the parameters remain practically unchanged. On one hand, a higher
 483 Re indicates that the ring is energetic and coherent, able to advect the bubble once it is
 484 captured. On the other hand, a higher We promotes bubble deformation. In particular, in
 485 this case, $We = 1$, meaning that the inertial stresses of the vortex ring are comparable to
 486 surface tension. This leads to bubble deformation, but not necessarily to its fragmentation.
 487 Therefore, the bubble can be seen to be drawn towards and captured inside the core region,
 488 it remains moving downwards within the ring for a certain time interval until it is finally
 489 released and continues its rise.

Figure 7: Top row: vertical velocity, u_y , of the vortex ring (u_v , red) and the bubble (u_b , black) for the cases regarding (a) weak interaction, (b) capture, drag and release, and (c) bubble breakup, respectively. Bottom row: temporal evolution of the bubble surface ratio, S/S_b , for the cases regarding (d) weak interaction, (e) capture, drag and release, and (f) bubble breakup, respectively. Dotted and dashed lines in (c) and (f) show daughter bubbles' velocities and surfaces, respectively. The interaction time is highlighted in grey.

490 Case III, illustrated in figure 6(c), corresponds to the most intense interaction: the bubble
 491 is trapped in the vortex core and remains inside for a relatively long time. In this case, inertial
 492 stresses are sufficient to overcome the restoring action of surface tension ($We \approx 0.8$), so the
 493 bubble elongates azimuthally along the ring until it eventually collapses into two fragments
 494 that stretch along the core, as will be demonstrated later. Note that, although We is lower
 495 than in Case II (but still close to unity), it can lead to bubble fragmentation. The fact that
 496 the core is thinner ($a_0/R_0 = 0.28$ and $a_0/R_b = 1.18$ in Case III, while $a_0/R_b = 1.71$ in
 497 Case II) is also a key feature promoting bubble breakup, since the ring's straining region is
 498 more concentrated, producing sharper, more powerful localised stretching of the bubble due
 499 to more abrupt velocity gradients.

500 As a first stage of the analysis of three cases, we present in figure 7 the evolution of the
 501 vertical velocities, $u_y(t)$, of both the vortex ring, $u_v(t)$, and the bubble, $u_b(t)$ (see figure 7,
 502 a-c), in dimensionless form, as well as the bubble surface ratio, $S(t)/S_b$ (see figure 7, d-f),
 503 with S_b the initial bubble surface obtained from the bubble formation recordings of the
 504 additional camera in figure 2(a), and $S(t)$ the surface of the reconstructed bubble at time t . In
 505 all cases, the vortex slows down as it moves downstream. The bubble accelerates quickly and
 506 suddenly, and then its velocity decreases sharply when it encounters the vortex ring. Note that
 507 the availability of time-resolved data for the trajectory of the bubble allows us to calculate
 508 the duration of the interaction: we define the beginning of the interaction, $t = 0$, from the
 509 moment the bubble deviates from its rising path due to the presence of the vortex ring, and
 510 its final, t_f , when the bubble turns back to its stationary rise and leaves its influence, being
 511 the interaction time $t_i = t_f$. We marked the starting and final points of the interaction time
 512 (shaded area in figure 7) by looking for peaks and inflection points in the bubble velocity,
 513 representing strong, fast deviations from the previous path and thus indicating the influence
 514 of the vortex ring on the bubble.

515 The bubble recovers its terminal velocity after being released by the vortex in Cases I and

Figure 8: (a) Three-dimensional and (b) top views of the bubble trajectory (thick solid line) and time evolution of the shape and position of the vortex ring core centre (thin dotted lines) in the weak interaction case (Case I). Both are coloured by time (see colourbar), with the bubble travelling upwards and the vortex downwards (counterflow). (c) Temporal evolution of the azimuthally averaged radial position of the vortex core centre and inner/outer limits, together with the bubble centroid. The shaded area in panel (c) corresponds to the duration of the interaction.

516 II (figures 7 a, b). In Case III (figure 7c), the bubble is trapped by the vortex core, which
 517 dramatically slows its velocity and causes it to break into two smaller bubbles (dashed and
 518 dotted lines in figures 7 c, f). These daughter bubbles are then dragged by the vortex at its
 519 own velocity. Regarding the bubble surface, in Cases I and II (figures. 7 d, e), it remains
 520 nearly constant because the bubble is barely deformed during its interaction with the vortex,
 521 as will be described later. Nevertheless, in Case III (figure 7f), the mother bubble is strongly
 522 elongated within the vortex core before breaking up (S/S_b increases up to ≈ 2). The bubble
 523 splits into two unequal daughter bubbles: one with approximately the same area as the
 524 mother bubble (dotted line), and another with nearly half the area (dashed line). The surfaces
 525 of both bubbles decrease slightly over time, suggesting that their surfaces are being restored,
 526 becoming more spherical, due to surface tension effects, as these bubbles are smaller than
 527 the mother bubble (and thus their corresponding Weber numbers are also smaller).

528 In the following, we will analyse in detail the kinematics and dynamics of each type of
 529 interaction obtained from the experimental data.

530

3.2. Case I: weak interaction

531 Figure 8 shows the temporal evolution of both the vortex ring core centre and the bubble
 532 position corresponding to a weak interaction. In particular, panels (a) and (b) illustrate the
 533 spatial evolution of both the vortex ring and the bubble, coloured by dimensionless time,
 534 $t\Gamma_0/R_0^2$. Note that we are able to solve the three-dimensional bubble trajectory as well as the
 535 position and the shape of the vortex ring: while the three-dimensional evolution is depicted

Figure 9: Temporal evolution of the azimuthal distribution of the (a) circulation, $\Gamma/(U_0 R_0)$, (b) planar, specific kinetic energy, $E_{k,A}^s R_0^2/(\rho \Gamma_0^2)$, and (c) planar, specific azimuthal enstrophy, $\Omega_{\theta,A}^s R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2$, of the weak interaction case (Case I). The values correspond to planar azimuthal sections covering two cores with $\theta \in [0^\circ, 180^\circ]$ (full plane), as it would be obtained in 2D-PIV measurements. The areas enclosed by black dashed lines mark the instants and azimuthal coordinates corresponding to the position of the bubble, θ_{bubble} , while the solid ones correspond to its position while it remains inside the vortex core during the interaction. The dotted vertical lines indicate the instants corresponding to different snapshots throughout the experiment (d to g, matched by colour) for a better understanding of the effect of the interaction. The bubble surface is coloured in magenta, while blue represents the λ_2 -criterion iso-surfaces (opaque blue: $\lambda_2 R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2 = -1.08$; faded blue: $\lambda_2 R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2 = -0.0072$). A supplementary movie related to this figure (Movie5_caseI.mp4) is accessible at journals.cambridge.org.

536 in panel (a), the top view is shown in (b). The vortex ring core (thin dotted lines) propagates
 537 downwards, while the bubble (thick solid line) travels upwards. The bubble, initially rising
 538 vertically along the y -axis, is pulled laterally away from the axis towards the core of the
 539 approaching vortex ring. In particular, when both the bubble and the ring are close enough,
 540 the bubble quickly deviates to its core, but it escapes very soon. The interaction time is short
 541 according to figures 8(a), (b), where it is observed that the interval of time when the bubble
 542 and vortex coincide in both colour and position is brief. This interaction time is highlighted
 543 with a shaded area in figure 8(c), where the time evolution of the radial position of the bubble
 544 centroid (blue), the outer and inner limits of the vortex core (black), and its centre (red)
 545 are plotted. The bubble interacts with the vortex at $t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 = 0$, and quickly moves towards
 546 the core centre, i.e., the radial position increases. Subsequently, after a very short period,
 547 its radial position deeply decreases, and the bubble escapes the core at the interaction time,
 548 $t_i \Gamma_0/R_0^2 \simeq 6$. Regarding the vortex ring, it maintains an almost circular form at each moment
 549 (figure 8), with a radius $R(t)$ that slightly grows over time after the perturbation (red line in
 550 figure 8c). Moreover, the ring centre deviates towards the interaction position (see figure 8b).
 551 This minimal distortion is expected in a weak interaction scenario, which fails to induce
 552 significant and lasting azimuthal instability or fragmentation in the vortex core.

553 Figure 9 presents dimensionless circulation, $\Gamma/(U_0 R_0)$ in (a), planar, specific kinetic

554 energy, $E_{k,A}^s R_0^2 / (\rho \Gamma_0^2)$ in (b) and planar, specific azimuthal enstrophy, $\Omega_{\theta,A}^s R_0^4 / (\rho \Gamma_0^2)$, in (c)
 555 as a θ -time map. We also include three-dimensional snapshots corresponding to specific time
 556 instants (d-g). The angle $\Delta\theta = \theta - \theta(t = 0)$ describes the position relative to the azimuthal
 557 coordinate of the centroid of the bubble at the beginning of the interaction. This means
 558 that $\Delta\theta$ defines the azimuthal extension of the bubble. Note that planar kinetic energy and
 559 azimuthal enstrophy in a particular θ and time correspond to equations (2.5) averaged in (y, r)
 560 planes covering 180° (full planes). The orientation of the planes where these magnitudes are
 561 calculated is varied from $-90^\circ < \Delta\theta < 90^\circ$ to span the entire ring and locate the interaction
 562 at the centre of the domain. This planar analysis in covering the two cores of the vortex make
 563 our results comparable to those a 2D study could obtain.

564 It is important to observe that for any azimuthal location, after a rapid decrease following
 565 the interaction, all three magnitudes show a continuous, gradual decay over time due to
 566 the weakening of the vortex as it descends. This implies that the interaction is not highly
 567 disruptive to the overall strength and long-term coherence of the vortex ring, in agreement
 568 with previous studies (Biswas & Govardhan 2022). Moreover, it can be noted that, close
 569 to the bubble region, θ_{bubble} , all magnitudes, but mostly enstrophy, are slightly perturbed
 570 along θ , thus revealing the three-dimensional nature of the interaction. The sharp localisation
 571 indicates that the most intense modification occurs exactly where the bubble momentarily
 572 resides (black line), failing to spread significantly along the circumference of the vortex core
 573 due to the weakness of the interaction. This implies that, when performing two-dimensional
 574 experiments, unless the measuring plane crosses the bubble, the results may be inaccurate if
 575 the interaction is weak.

576 The λ_2 -criterion iso-surfaces (Jeong & Hussain 1995) plotted in figure 9(d)-(g) correspond
 577 to four different instants: slightly before (d), during (e), right after (f), and long after (g) the
 578 interaction. These instants are highlighted with vertical dashed lines in figures 9(a)-(c). The
 579 vortex core structure can be visualised in these snapshots, showing that the ring remains
 580 highly coherent throughout the interaction, although it loses intensity. However, a remarkable
 581 loss of vorticity at the core centre can be observed by the reduction of opaque blue structures,
 582 although the vortex ring structure remains almost intact. Even though the interaction with
 583 the bubble is brief and localised, it triggers a strong decay of the vorticity in the core. These
 584 snapshots also confirm that the bubble (magenta surface) is attracted towards the vortex
 585 core but appears intact and unbroken upon the closest approach. This absence of rupture
 586 is consistent with the interaction being subcritical, as bubble breakup generally requires
 587 $We \gtrsim 1$ for $R_0/R_b > 1$ (Foronda-Trillo *et al.* 2021). In fact, notice that the bubble covers a
 588 nearly constant azimuthal extension throughout the interaction (black solid lines in the maps
 589 of figures 9a-c), indicating no remarkable shape deformations of the bubble surface. Note
 590 that a change of the extension of the azimuthal planes covered by the bubble could indicate
 591 not only a real shape alteration but also a radial motion of the bubble: for a given shape,
 592 the bubble covers a larger extension in the azimuthal coordinate when it moves to a smaller
 593 radial position, and *vice versa* (see figure 1b). In fact, the decrease that takes place prior to
 594 the interaction corresponds to the bubble motion towards the core (higher radial position),
 595 while the increase after the interaction corresponds to the migration away from the core
 596 towards the central vertical axis, in agreement with figure 8(c).

597

598 The previous maps indicate that the bubble effect in this case is localised around the
 599 collision area. To further contrast the effect on the flow variables in this area (θ_{bubble}) to
 600 the rest of the planes, where no bubble is present, we averaged them azimuthally, making a
 601 distinction between bubble and no-bubble azimuthal planes (red and blue lines, respectively

Figure 10: (Top row) Temporal evolution of dimensionless (a) circulation, (b) specific, kinetic energy, and (c) specific enstrophy in Case I (weak interaction). Results in planes with or without bubble are depicted in red and blue, respectively. Figures (b) and (c) show the azimuthal average of the corresponding 2D variable averaged in half-planes (red and blue) together with their 3D volumetric counterpart (black). The shaded areas correspond to the duration of the interaction. The black dotted lines mark the instants corresponding to different events throughout the experiment. (Bottom row) Velocity field and vorticity contours of the four instants marked in the top-row figures, on a vertical plane at $\theta = 56^\circ$. The silhouette of the bubble is depicted in green. The bubble crosses this plane at all the depicted instants, but to a different extent depending on its azimuthal position and deformation at such instant (see the different sizes and shapes of the silhouettes in d-f).

602 in figures 10(a)-(c), calculated with equations 2.5)†, and separating the information in half-
603 planes ($\theta \in [0^\circ, 360^\circ]$). Although the interaction is brief, notice that the bubble alters
604 the vortex characteristics while it occurs (red line). Circulation is observed to be slightly
605 enhanced during the interaction in the planes where the bubble is present, while significantly
606 larger values of enstrophy and, mainly, kinetic energy are observed at the beginning of
607 the interaction (red lines). As soon as the bubble starts moving away from the vortex core
608 due to buoyancy, there is a quick drop of the enstrophy peak, reaching the value of the
609 no-bubble planes (blue lines). At the same time, a decrease in energy happens, which may
610 be understood as the bubble slowing down the vortex due to a wake effect. Thus, we can
611 appreciate in the three graphs an evident change of slope to a steeper decay of the flow
612 variables when the bubble is present, indicating that, despite the encounter being brief, the
613 vortex loses strength due to its collision with the bubble. This effect, where the vortex is
614 weakened by the interaction, aligns with findings from other studies, such as the experimental
615 work by Jha & Govardhan (2015). Here, they reported a large reduction in enstrophy and
616 a significant drop in the vortex convection speed in low-Weber-number cases where the
617 bubble was briefly trapped, contrasting with negligible effects seen at higher We . This
618 highlights the importance of performing measurements precisely in the azimuthal planes

† Note that, in these figures we only include the components of the velocity in the measuring plane to compute the kinetic energy and vorticity component perpendicular to the plane in the enstrophy, like in two-dimensional PIV measurements. However, since we perform three-dimensional measurements, the three components of the velocity and vorticity could have been obtained.

619 where the interaction occurs. This is feasible in three-dimensional experiments, where the
 620 interaction plane can be identified and selected afterwards. In contrast, in two-dimensional
 621 experiments, the measurement plane is fixed and may not coincide with the actual plane of
 622 interaction between the bubble and the vortex. In this regard, the volume-averaged 3D value
 623 in the kinetic energy and enstrophy, equations (2.6), are included in figures 10(b) and (c),
 624 respectively (black line). Note that the volumetric metrics integrate over the 3D fluid volume,
 625 accounting for all three components of velocity and, thus, vorticity. While planar magnitudes
 626 clearly show the impact of interaction with the bubble, three-dimensional magnitudes depict
 627 smoother evolution, although they display the changes in the kinetic energy and the total
 628 enstrophy when the bubble faces the vortex ring. Nevertheless, the decay of both magnitudes
 629 over time reflects the overall evolution of the vortex ring correctly.

630 The velocity field and vorticity of the four instants selected in figure 10 (a)-(c), along
 631 with the vorticity contours and the bubble surface, are shown in figures 10 (d)-(g). Note
 632 that we selected a plane containing the bubble at all times in order to characterise its effect.
 633 However, due to the azimuthal motion of the bubble over time, its presence may only be
 634 partial at certain instants, depending on whether the plane crosses it far from the centroid.
 635 As expected, high velocities are observed around the vortex core, while the liquid is almost
 636 stagnant far from the vortex ring. It can be observed that, in the pre-interaction and capture
 637 stages (figures 10 d and e, respectively), the vortex structure remains almost unchanged in
 638 terms of its shape and amount of vorticity. However, because of the bubble interaction, the
 639 vorticity of the core is heavily distorted locally once the bubble escapes (figure 10 f). Finally,
 640 the vortex continues to translate downwards, but, although still coherent, with a weakened
 641 core (figure 10 g).

642 3.3. Case II: Capture, drag and release

643 We will now describe a stronger interaction case, with higher Re and We than Case I, but
 644 similar vortex core-to-radius ratio, a_0/R_0 . Figures 11(a)-(b) describe the position of the
 645 vortex-bubble pair over time. As can be observed in the bubble path (thick time-coloured
 646 line in figures 11a, b and blue line in c), the bubble travels upwards first and then is dragged
 647 laterally to larger radial positions when it is close enough to the vortex ($t = 0$). During a
 648 certain time, the bubble is trapped inside the core (see figures 11b, c) and travels downwards
 649 together with the vortex (see the period where the bubble path and the vortex contour are the
 650 same colour in figures 11a and b). Meanwhile, the presence of the bubble weakens the vortex
 651 core, introducing shape distortions. When the vortex is no longer powerful enough to hold
 652 the bubble in its core, the bubble is released and rises again (figure 11a). This interaction
 653 eventually leads to a destabilisation of the vortex ring structure. This is most evident in
 654 figures 11(a) and (b), where at later times (reddish colours), the vortex no longer shows
 655 a circular shape. Additionally, in figure 11(c), at the moment the bubble leaves the ring
 656 ($t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \approx 22$), the position of the vortex core (shown by the red and black lines) exhibits
 657 some distortion due to the ring structure no longer being discernible. Note that the interaction
 658 time is significantly longer in this case than in Case I, due to the higher vortex circulation
 659 and lower pressure in the core.

660 The evolution of circulation, planar, specific energy and planar, specific enstrophy are
 661 depicted in figure 12, together with the bubble position (black line enclosed area). As in
 662 Case I, circulation decreases over time, with no notable effects of the bubble during the
 663 initial stage of the interaction. However, after some contact between the ring and the bubble
 664 ($t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \gtrsim 14$), the circulation starts to decrease more rapidly. This effect is even more evident
 665 in kinetic energy and enstrophy (figures 12b and c, respectively), with a steep decrease in
 666 their magnitude, which started much earlier ($t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \approx 5$). Unlike in the previous case, it is
 667 also notable that the effects on the vortex ring are not limited to the vicinity of the bubble,

Figure 11: (a) Three-dimensional and (b) top views of the bubble trajectory (thick solid line) and time evolution of the shape and position of the vortex ring core centre (thin dotted lines) in the capture and drag case (Case II). Both are coloured by time (see colourbar), with the bubble travelling upwards and the vortex downwards (counterflow). (c) Temporal evolution of the azimuthally averaged radial position of the vortex core centre and inner/outer limits, together with the bubble centroid. The shaded area in panel (c) corresponds to the duration of the interaction.

668 but extend more globally around θ . The value of the Weber number ($We = 1$) is not high
 669 enough to cause the bubble to break up. This may be due to the thickness of the vortex
 670 ($a_0/R_0 = 0.38$), which makes it weaker than a thinner vortex with the same Re . Note that
 671 the result of the interaction and some differences between the cases may also be caused by
 672 factors not included in the scope of this work, such as the relative position of the bubble and
 673 the vortex at the beginning of the interaction.

674 Regarding the bubble position, before the interaction (dashed lines in figures 12a-c), we can
 675 see the bubble drifting back and forth from its initial position (covering different azimuthal
 676 extension), indicating it has an unstable path (see also figure 11a). Right after that (see
 677 the change from the dashed to the solid line), the bubble suffers an attraction towards the
 678 vortex core at a higher radial distance (see also figure 11c), covering thus a lower azimuthal
 679 extension. Once inside the core, the bubble drifts azimuthally and then travels back closer to
 680 $\Delta\theta \approx 0$, where it stays until its release. This may be a consequence of the vortex ring losing
 681 intensity and coherence, as can be seen in figures 12(d)-(f) through the λ_2 criterion at four
 682 different instants. During capture and the initial bubble drag phase (figures 12d-e), the vortex
 683 structure retains its overall shape and level of vorticity. This period marks the beginning of
 684 intense interactions that strongly affect instantaneous liquid vortex properties. During the
 685 sustained drag (figure 12f), the shape and symmetry of the ring are distorted due to the
 686 presence of the trapped bubble, in agreement with figures 11(a)-(b). This distortion, while
 687 not yet causing major global circulation loss, reflects the strong perturbation introduced by
 688 the bubble. Figure 12(g) corresponds to the post-release stage, during which the vortex core

Figure 12: Temporal evolution of the azimuthal distribution of the (a) circulation, $\Gamma/(U_0 R_0)$, (b) planar, specific kinetic energy, $E_{k,A}^s R_0^2/(\rho \Gamma_0^2)$, and (c) planar, specific azimuthal enstrophy, $\Omega_{\theta,A}^s R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2$, of the capture+drag+release case (Case II). The values correspond to planar azimuthal sections covering two cores with $\theta \in [0^\circ, 180^\circ]$ (full planes), as it would be obtained in 2D-PIV measurements. The areas enclosed by black dashed lines mark the instants and azimuthal coordinates corresponding to the position of the bubble, θ_{bubble} , while the solid ones correspond to its position while it remains inside the vortex core during the interaction. The dotted vertical lines indicate the instants corresponding to different snapshots throughout the experiment (d to g, matched by colour) for a better understanding of the effect of the interaction. The bubble surface is coloured in magenta, while blue represents the λ_2 -criterion iso-surfaces (opaque blue: $\lambda_2 R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2 = -0.72$; faded blue: $\lambda_2 R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2 = -0.0036$). A supplementary movie related to this figure (Movie6_caseII.mp4) is accessible at journals.cambridge.org.

689 loses overall strength and coherence due to structural weakening. Regarding the bubble shape
 690 (magenta), note that although it is initially deformed at the beginning of the interaction due
 691 to the stresses induced by the vortex, they are not sufficiently high to induce its breakup.

692 To further analyse how the position of the bubble impacts the flow over time, we may look
 693 at figure 13. Here, we cannot identify any significant differences in the decay of circulation
 694 over time between planes with and without bubble (figure 13a), which is consistent with the
 695 findings by Jha & Govardhan (2015) for high enough Weber numbers and thick core vortices.
 696 However, a slight increase in circulation can be observed around $t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \approx 6$, probably due
 697 to the vorticity shed by the bubble when it starts to interact with the vortex ring. In contrast,
 698 we see a strong effect of the bubble in kinetic energy and azimuthal enstrophy. In the former
 699 (figure 13b), both the 3D evolution and the mean value of the 2D half-planes without bubble
 700 have a similar trend: a monotonic decrease over time, with a slightly steeper slope during the
 701 interaction period. However, the planes where the bubble interacts with the vortex show a
 702 significant loss of kinetic energy from the start of the interaction. This is a direct consequence
 703 of the perturbations introduced by the presence of the bubble, slowing down the vortex. In
 704 fact, figures 13(e) and (f) show how the vortex tilts with the core on the left side lower than
 705 that on the right, with the latter containing the bubble. Shortly before the bubble escapes from
 706 the vortex, the two-dimensional specific kinetic energy in the planes containing the bubble

Figure 13: (Top row) Temporal evolution of dimensionless (a) circulation, (b) specific kinetic energy, and (c) specific, azimuthal enstrophy in Case II (capture+drag+release). Results in planes with or without bubble are depicted in red and blue, respectively. Figures (b) and (c) show the azimuthal average of the corresponding 2D variable averaged in half-planes (red and blue) together with their 3D volumetric counterpart (black). The shaded areas correspond to the duration of the interaction. The black dotted lines mark the instants corresponding to different events throughout the experiment. (Bottom row) Velocity field and vorticity contours of the four instants marked in the top-row figures, on a vertical plane at $\theta = 61^\circ$. The silhouette of the bubble is depicted in green. The bubble crosses this plane at all the depicted instants, but to a different extent depending on its azimuthal position and deformation at such instant (see the different sizes and shapes of the silhouettes in d-g).

707 recovers to a value similar to that of the planes without bubble, exhibiting a bump (figure 13b).
 708 Note that the rate of decay of the three-dimensional, specific kinetic energy is also higher
 709 during interaction, which is consistent with direct numerical simulations by Foronda-Trillo
 710 *et al.* (2021). Regarding the time evolution of the azimuthal enstrophy, shown in figure 13(c),
 711 different trends are observed. In the planes containing the bubble, it initially decreases when
 712 the bubble starts to interact with the vortex ring. However, during this interaction, $\Omega_{\theta,A}^s$
 713 remains almost constant for a period of time before increasing as the bubble escapes from
 714 the vortex. This increase coincides with the rise of $E_{k,A}^s$ shown in figure 13(b). Differently, in
 715 planes which do not contain the bubble, a monotonic decrease of $\Omega_{\theta,A}^s$ is observed with time
 716 (blue line in figure 13c), with a slightly steeper slope during the interaction period. However,
 717 the volumetric enstrophy (black line in figure 13c) shows an increase at the beginning of the
 718 interaction, in agreement with the 3D numerical simulations by Foronda-Trillo *et al.* (2021).

719 Finally, the evolution of the vortex and how it loses energy can be further observed in the
 720 velocity and vorticity fields in a plane containing the bubble, represented in figures 13(d)-(g).
 721 Similarly to the previous case, here the bubble quickly approaches the ring and gets trapped
 722 (figures 13d-e). Unlike in the weak interaction case, instead of rapidly escaping, it is dragged
 723 downwards. In this interplay, the vortex level of vorticity is almost unaltered (figure 13f),
 724 but the shape and symmetry of the ring are heavily distorted. It is not until the bubble
 725 escapes (figure 13g) that the level of vorticity is importantly diminished. In summary, this

Figure 14: (a) Three-dimensional and (b) top views of the bubble trajectory (thick solid line) and time evolution of the shape and position of the vortex ring core centre (thin dotted lines) in the breakup case (Case III). Both are coloured by time (see colourbar), with the bubble travelling upwards and the vortex downwards (counterflow). (c) Temporal evolution of the azimuthally averaged radial position of the vortex core centre and inner/outer limits, together with the bubble centroid. The shaded area in panel (c) corresponds to the duration of the interaction.

726 case depicts a combination of local effects in the bubble surroundings, which then evolve to
 727 a strong global distortion of the vortex due to the presence of the bubble.

728

3.4. Case III: Bubble breakup

729 The last case in this work covers the strongest interaction: here, the vortex ring breaks the
 730 bubble into two daughter bubbles. The kinematics of this interaction are depicted in figure 14.
 731 The three-dimensional and top views show that initially, the bubble rises near the vertical
 732 axis of the vortex ring while the ring travels downwards (dark to light blue in figures 14 a, b).
 733 When they are close enough, the bubble is quickly deviated towards the ring core at $t = 0$ (see
 734 also figure 14c), and starts to travel downwards within the vortex core. In this case, the vortex
 735 is thinner than in Cases I and II, and although We is smaller than in Case II, it is large enough
 736 to overcome the confining surface tension forces acting on the bubble. Thus, after a very
 737 short time, the mother bubble splits into two daughter bubbles, which move in the azimuthal
 738 direction without leaving the vortex core for the duration of the experiment. Regarding the
 739 vortex ring, its circular shape remains largely unaltered, as shown in figures 14(a)-(b).

740 Figure 15 shows how the flow variables evolve with the azimuthal position of the bubble.
 741 Similarly to the previous cases, the evolution of the flow variables shown in figures 15(a)-(c)
 742 is characterised by a monotonic decay over time, which accelerates when the interaction begins.
 743 No particular effects on the temporal evolution of the circulation are spotted in figure 15(a),
 744 only slight changes appear along the azimuthal direction due to the perturbations induced
 745 by the bubbles. The kinetic energy (figure 15b) shows higher values in the area around the

Figure 15: Temporal evolution of the azimuthal distribution of the (a) circulation, $\Gamma/(U_0 R_0)$, (b) planar, specific kinetic energy, $E_{k,A}^s R_0^2/(\rho \Gamma_0^2)$, and (c) planar, specific azimuthal enstrophy, $\Omega_{\theta,A}^s R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2$, of the breakup case (Case III). The values correspond to planar azimuthal sections covering two cores with $\theta \in [0^\circ, 180^\circ]$ (full planes), as it would be obtained in 2D-PIV measurements. The areas enclosed by black dashed lines mark the instants and azimuthal coordinates corresponding to the position of the mother bubble, while the solid ones correspond to its position while it remains inside the vortex core during the interaction. After the mother bubble breaks, each of the daughter bubbles is marked with a different colour of the solid line (large bubble in purple and small bubble in magenta). The dotted vertical lines indicate the instants corresponding to different snapshots throughout the experiment (d to g, matched by colour) for a better understanding of the effect of the interaction. The bubble surface is coloured in magenta, while blue represents the λ_2 -criterion iso-surfaces (opaque blue: $\lambda_2 R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2 = -3.80$; faded blue: $\lambda_2 R_0^4/\Gamma_0^2 = -0.0038$). A supplementary movie related to this figure (Movie7_caseIII.mp4) is accessible at journals.cambridge.org.

746 bubble at the moment of capture. After this peak, the value quickly stabilises globally around
 747 the azimuth. Finally, the azimuthal enstrophy (figure 15c) is much more strongly affected
 748 by the presence of the bubble, particularly during its breakup. Before the interaction, it
 749 displays a nearly uniform distribution around θ . However, when the interaction begins, it
 750 concentrates at the area of the bubble, while decreasing in the surroundings. It even increases
 751 and peaks a few instants before breakup, after which it quickly drops. This increase in
 752 enstrophy is associated with the bubble elongation within the vortex core. Moreover, the
 753 enstrophy remains higher around the daughter bubbles than elsewhere in the ring throughout
 754 the experiment, particularly in the area of the largest daughter bubble (purple solid line
 755 in figure 15c). This indicates that even though the vortex structure in this case remains
 756 coherent, as can be noticed in figures 15(d)-(g), and thus less affected by the bubble, it
 757 gets perturbed, shedding vorticity, especially due to large bubbles trapped in the core (see
 758 figure 15g). These flow features could not have been extracted from a two-dimensional PIV
 759 experiment. If we focus now on the bubble dynamics, it shows a motion around the central
 760 axis before the interaction (black dashed line in figures 15a-c): initially, the bubble covers
 761 all the $\Delta\theta$ values because it is at the centre of the axial axis (see also figure 15d). A few
 762 instants later (figure 15e), the bubble rises to a vertical position a few bubble diameters

Figure 16: (Top row) Temporal evolution of dimensionless (a) circulation, (b) specific kinetic energy, and (c) specific azimuthal enstrophy in the Case III (bubble breakup). Results in planes with or without bubble are depicted in red and blue, respectively. Figures (b) and (c) show the azimuthal average of the corresponding 2D variable averaged in half-planes (red and blue) together with their 3D volumetric counterpart (black). The shaded areas correspond to the duration of the interaction. The black dotted lines mark the instants corresponding to different events throughout the experiment, and the green dotted line marks the breakup time. (Bottom row) Velocity field and vorticity contours of the four instants marked in the top-row figures, on a vertical plane at $\theta = 25^\circ$. The silhouette of the bubble is depicted in green. The bubble crosses this plane at all the depicted instants, but to a different extent depending on its azimuthal position and deformation at such instant (see the different sizes and shapes of the silhouettes in d-g).

763 below the vortex ring, where it starts to be influenced by its velocity. At $t = 0$, it is quickly
 764 dragged laterally into the vortex core (see also figure 14c). In fact, note that the azimuthal area
 765 covered by the bubble (solid black line in figures 15(a)-(c)) rapidly decreases to a minimum of
 766 $\theta_{bubble} \sim 90^\circ$. It is after this minimum in the spread of the bubble in θ (see figure 15e) that
 767 it grows again due to an azimuthal elongation of the bubble along the ring core (see figure
 768 15f). The sequence of capture, elongation, and subsequent breakup observed here aligns
 769 closely with the description given by (Jha & Govardhan 2015), who detailed a four-stage
 770 interaction process in which a bubble is attracted to the low-pressure core, elongates due to
 771 azimuthal pressure gradients, and eventually breaks. The elongation is a consequence of the
 772 bubble perturbing the pressure distribution inside the core: the pressure rises at the location
 773 of the bubble, creating a pressure difference along the azimuthal direction that causes the
 774 bubble to expand along θ (Martínez-Bazán 2015; Biswas & Govardhan 2022, 2023; Zhang
 775 *et al.* 2023), covering approximately up to one third of the circumference of the ring (see
 776 figure 15f). The elongation stage is very short, because the bubble quickly breaks into two
 777 parts (see purple and magenta solid lines in figures 15(a)-(c) at $t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \approx 7$). These daughter
 778 bubbles have different sizes, and their spread in θ tends to reduce after breakup, given that
 779 the surface tension is strong enough to restore the spherical-to-ellipsoidal shape of the bubbles
 780 (see figure 15g). They also exhibit a drift along θ , like in the interaction of a vortex ring with
 781 a solid particle (Biswas & Govardhan 2025).

782 Now, we summarise the effect of the bubble on the flow characteristics by examining
 783 how the averaged values of kinetic energy and enstrophy differ in half-planes where the

784 bubble interacts with vortex motion, compared to half-planes free of interaction, alongside
 785 their three-dimensional counterparts. Figure 16 (a) shows that, as seen before, circulation is
 786 hardly affected by the bubble, with a moderate decay in time. The planar, specific kinetic
 787 energy (see figure 16b) also decays, in both planes with and without the bubble. However, it
 788 undergoes a significant change in slope a few moments after the bubble breaks up (marked
 789 by a green dotted line in figures 16a-c). In the planes with a bubble (red line), the energy
 790 is redistributed near the bubble, which results in a slight increase in energy, which quickly
 791 drops before breakup and then recovers to the same value as the rest of the ring, in agreement
 792 with figure 15(b). Note also the rapid decrease of $E_{k,A}^s$ around $t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \approx 3.3$ in the planes
 793 containing the bubble. By looking at the snapshots in figures 16(d)-(f), we may observe that
 794 the liquid velocity (and thus the kinetic energy) does not show a strong difference when
 795 the bubble starts to enter the vortex (figures 16 d-e). However, the values of both velocity
 796 and energy are much smaller when the bubble is in its equilibrium radial position inside the
 797 core for a sufficiently long time. (figure 16f). Similarly to the previous cases, the volumetric
 798 kinetic energy is reduced, and its temporal decay is similar but smoother than that of its
 799 planar counterpart, although it also shows the change of slope after the bubble breakup.

800 Finally, regarding enstrophy (figure 16c), there is a significant increase from the moment
 801 the bubble is attracted by the vortex at $t = 0$ (see also figure 16e). This increase in enstrophy
 802 is associated with the kinetic energy decrease observed at around $t\Gamma_0/R_0^2 \approx 3.3$. The growth
 803 in enstrophy is fairly maintained until the bubble reaches its maximum elongation (see
 804 figure 16f). Afterwards, the enstrophy decreases. Following the breakup, the enstrophy in the
 805 bubble half-planes (red line) begins to decay more quickly than before the bubble breakup.
 806 This decay is even more pronounced in the no-bubble planes (blue line). This indicates not
 807 only the growth of vorticity near the bubbles, but also its redistribution from the rest of the
 808 ring towards the bubble areas, as shown on the map in figure 15(c). In figure 16 (g), the
 809 level of vorticity has diminished notably after breakup. Regarding the evolution of three-
 810 dimensional enstrophy, its behaviour is a combination of planar enstrophy in planes with
 811 and without a bubble. It also shows an increase in enstrophy when the vortex ring traps the
 812 bubble. It is worth mentioning that the evolution of kinetic energy and azimuthal enstrophy
 813 in Cases II and III are very much alike, which may be expected due to their similar Re and
 814 R_0/R_b values and relatively high We . The main difference between them is a_0/R_b , with Case
 815 III presenting a thinner core, which indicates that core thickness is a key feature to enable
 816 bubble breakup.

817

3.5. Comparative analysis

818 Figure 17 directly compares the latter magnitudes in the $\Delta\theta - t$ planes for three interaction
 819 cases. If we focus on circulation (left column), Case II figure 17(d) shows significantly
 820 larger values compared to Cases I and III (figures 17 a and g, respectively), which can be
 821 attributed to the initial strength of the vortex generated for that experiment. In fact, Case
 822 II was intentionally set up with the highest circulation strength, resulting in the largest
 823 Reynolds number among the three scenarios. Although all magnitudes decay over time,
 824 circulation is the magnitude least affected by the bubble interaction. This means that the
 825 ranking established by the initial vortex strength (Case II > Case III > Case I) is maintained
 826 throughout the measurement time.

827 Nevertheless, the planar, specific kinetic energy level (central column of figure 17) is much
 828 higher in Case III (figure 17h) compared to Cases I and II (figure 17 b and e, respectively)
 829 primarily because Case III involves an interaction with a vortex ring that has initially a higher
 830 kinetic energy (see Table 2) and a thinner core, which concentrates the flow variables more
 831 intensely. Moreover, kinetic energy in Case III (figure 17h) shows higher values in the area

Figure 17: Temporal evolution of the azimuthal distribution of the dimensionless circulation (left column), planar specific kinetic energy (central column), and planar specific azimuthal entrophy (right column) for Case I (first row), Case II (second row), and Case III (third row).

832 around the bubble at the moment of capture. This greater kinetic energy is related to the
 833 vorticity emitted by the bubble during the capture process, which consists first in stopping
 834 the bubble rise and then being directed towards the bubble core (see figure 15e). In this case,
 835 the bubble changes its velocity more abruptly, which could explain the raise of the kinetic
 836 energy. After this initial peak, the kinetic energy magnitude quickly stabilises globally around
 837 the azimuth, maintaining a high level compared to the rapidly decaying energy found in the
 838 strongly distorted vortex core of Case II (figure 17e).

839 Levels of specific azimuthal entrophy (right column of figure 17) are observed to be
 840 the highest also in Case III (figure 17i), compared to Cases I and II (figure 17 c and f,
 841 respectively). This fact is mainly due to the specific vortex properties of Case III and the
 842 mechanism of intense vorticity concentration and stretching leading up to the bubble rupture.
 843 A thinner core structure means that the vortex principal vorticity is concentrated in a smaller
 844 cross-sectional area (Biswas & Govardhan 2023). This concentration leads to higher vorticity
 845 (and entrophy) when measured in a cross-sectional plane. In contrast, only a brief, localised
 846 perturbation occurs in Case I (figure 17c). In Case II (figure 17f), the azimuthal entrophy

Figure 18: Evolution of (a) circulation, (b) specific, volumetric, kinetic energy, and (c) specific, volumetric, total entrophy over time for a base case of vortex ring without bubble ($Re = 28000$, $a_0/R_0 = 0.29$) and the different interaction cases studied: Case I (weak interaction), Case II (capture, drag, release) and Case III (bubble breakup). Coloured areas indicate interaction intervals. The vertical green dotted line denotes breakup time in Case III. Note that to compare the evolution of the different regimes, the flow variables are normalized to their initial value and the time scales start at $t - t_0$, with t_0 the initial time of the experiment, when the vortex has completely entered our measurement volume.

847 is lower because the effect of the thin core is absent, what spreads the flow variables over a
848 larger area.

849 The three interaction cases show distinct responses that may be defined in terms of
850 variations in the vortex volumetric ring magnitudes. In this regard, figure 18 compares
851 the evolution of (a) circulation (Γ), (b) specific volumetric kinetic energy ($E_{k,V}^s$), and (c)
852 specific total volumetric entrophy (Ω_V^s) for the base vortex ring (without a bubble) and the
853 three distinct interaction cases. The duration of the kinematic interaction is also highlighted
854 in figure 18 through the shaded areas. As explained before, the volumetric magnitudes
855 reflect the overall average evolution and long-term coherence of the vortex ring. Note that
856 circulation (figure 18a) is the integral property least affected by the presence and interaction
857 of the bubble, with the decay over time similar for all cases. However, in Case I, in which
858 the vortex does not have enough energy to attract and disturb the bubble, the circulation
859 decreases abruptly after the interaction due to the disturbance introduced by the bubble.

860 Regarding kinetic energy (figure 18b), all interaction cases exhibit an enhanced decay rate
861 when compared to the base case, signifying that the bubble interaction leads to a general loss
862 of strength in the vortex. In Case I, the interaction is characterised by a brief encounter with
863 the bubble. However, the vortex still loses strength, resulting in a steeper decay slope than in
864 the base case. This aligns with the observation that cases with a low Weber number result
865 in overall weakening. (Jha & Govardhan 2015). The decay rate for Cases II and III is larger
866 during the interaction, and it slows down after release or breakup, respectively, suggesting a
867 significant loss of kinetic energy from the beginning of the capture process.

868 Volumetric total entrophy (Ω_V^s) is the integral property most strongly affected by the
869 bubble interaction. Notice that, in the three cases, Ω_V^s increases when the vortex starts to
870 interact with the bubble, showing a bump in the time evolution. This is more evident in
871 Cases II and III, since the beginning of the vortex-bubble interaction in Case I is close
872 to the start of the recording time. After this rapid increase, the total volumetric entrophy
873 decreases at a rate larger than the base case, i.e. the single vortex ring (see Foronda-Trillo
874 *et al.* 2021). The overall reduction in Case I highlights a loss of strength consistent with large
875 entrophy reductions seen in moderate-Reynolds and low-Weber-number cases, even in brief
876 interactions (Martínez-Bazán 2015).

877 Finally, since we are performing 3D experiments, we are able to characterise not only the
878 contribution of the azimuthal component of the vorticity to the entrophy, $\Omega_{\theta,V}^s$ but also the

Figure 19: Specific volumetric enstrophy contributions of each vorticity component, together with the specific, total, volumetric enstrophy for (a) Case I, (b) Case II, and (c) Case III. Note that a different scale is used for the global and azimuthal enstrophy (left), and the radial and axial ones (right).

879 radial and axial contributions, $\Omega_{r,V}^s$ and $\Omega_{y,V}^s$, respectively. Indeed, as shown in figure 19, the
 880 azimuthal contribution is the major one to the total enstrophy, being the radial and axial ones
 881 less relevant. As commented before, the volumetric enstrophy is the vortex ring property
 882 most strongly affected by the interaction, providing a global measure of the dissipation rate
 883 of kinetic energy and reflecting the overall coherence of the vortex ring. In fact, the kinetic
 884 energy of the flow is lost mainly through the creation of small-scale vorticity, that is, through
 885 an increase of enstrophy. The analysis of the contribution of the three vorticity components
 886 is crucial for understanding the three-dimensional effects of the vortex-bubble interaction.

887 In Case I, an increase in both Ω_V^s and $\Omega_{\theta,V}^s$ can be observed during the vortex-bubble
 888 interaction time, which then drops sharply afterwards. This drop $\Omega_{\theta,V}^s$ is accompanied by a
 889 slight increase in $\Omega_{r,V}^s$ and $\Omega_{y,V}^s$, indicating that there is a redistribution of low-scale vorticity
 890 due to the three-dimensionality introduced by the presence of the bubble. Nevertheless, the
 891 contributions of the radial and axial vorticity components to the total enstrophy are much
 892 lower than that of the azimuthal component, and they are unable to compensate for the loss of
 893 Ω_V^s . This is probably due to the limitations in the spatial resolution of the three-dimensional
 894 measurements, unable to resolve the smallest vorticity scales. In Cases II and III, there is also
 895 an increase of enstrophy during the interaction time, more evident in Ω_V^s than in $\Omega_{\theta,V}^s$ due
 896 to the contributions of $\Omega_{r,V}^s$ and $\Omega_{y,V}^s$. In these cases, the deformation and/or breakup of the
 897 bubble contributes to the destabilisation of the vortex ring by generating small-scale radial
 898 and axial vorticity, which increases $\Omega_{r,V}^s$ and $\Omega_{y,V}^s$, and consequently the total enstrophy,
 899 Ω_V^s . This fact, which is especially remarkable in Case III, aligns with the results from
 900 three-dimensional numerical simulations (Foronda-Trillo *et al.* 2021).

901 4. Conclusions

902 We present an experimental study on the interaction of a bubble and a vortex ring in different
 903 scenarios, corresponding to different values of the governing parameters, Re , We , a_0/R_0
 904 and R_0/R_b . An experimental three-dimensional approach was chosen to characterise the
 905 volumetric nature of the problem and track bubble motion within the field of view.
 906 Specifically, we used the 4D-LPT technique based on the Shake-The-Box algorithm to
 907 obtain the liquid 3D velocity field, and we reconstructed the bubble with a tomographic
 908 algorithm (MxLOS). We applied these techniques to 4-camera and 6-camera sets of images,
 909 respectively, providing multiple points of view for an accurate inspection of the volume. We
 910 analysed the obtained velocity fields using several vortex identification algorithms available in
 911 the literature and calculated the relevant flow variables, i.e., the position and size of the vortex,

912 and the circulation, kinetic energy, and enstrophy in the flow. Additionally, we distinguished
913 two ways of expressing energy and enstrophy: by their classical volumetric definition or with
914 their 2D counterparts, computed on a planar domain comprising an azimuthal cut of the
915 volume. The latter is the equivalent of the information that could be obtained from a 2D-PIV
916 experiment.

917 We compared three cases of counter-flow collision between a bubble of given size
918 and different vortex rings, featuring the most common behaviours we found within our
919 experiments: Case I, depicting a weak interaction, where neither the bubble nor the vortex
920 were strongly affected; Case II, where the bubble was captured and dragged by the vortex
921 and the latter was strongly distorted due to the presence of the bubble inside its core; and
922 Case III, involving a stronger vortex able to capture the bubble and break it into two pieces
923 without a severe loss of energy in the core.

924 The bubble-vortex interaction in Case I is brief and non-disruptive. Flow variables showed
925 a continuous, gradual decay due to viscous diffusion, after a sharper decay due to the bubble
926 interaction. The effect was highly localised around the bubble position, failing to spread
927 significantly along the vortex circumference. This fact complicates addressing this type of
928 interaction through 2D-PIV. The 3D enstrophy behaves as an average between 2D half-planes
929 with and without the bubble. In Case II, with higher Re and We , the bubble is captured,
930 dragged for a finite time, and then released. The interaction caused the vortex structure to be
931 strongly distorted. Flow variables, particularly kinetic energy and enstrophy, show a steep
932 decay starting earlier, and their effects extend more globally around the azimuthal direction,
933 indicating a stronger, sustained interaction. The rate of decay of the volumetric kinetic
934 energy was larger during the interaction, and volumetric enstrophy shows an increase at the
935 beginning of the interaction. In Case III, the combination of sufficient inertial stress (high Re)
936 and a thinner core allowed the vortex to trap the bubble and stretch it azimuthally, leading
937 to fragmentation into two daughter bubbles. This case behaves very similarly to Case II,
938 showing significant dynamics in enstrophy: it concentrated heavily in the bubble area, peaked
939 just before breakup (related to azimuthal elongation), and subsequently dropped quickly. The
940 3D enstrophy here revealed an interplay between global decay and near-bubble local effects.
941 Furthermore, all cases have depicted an increase of the non-azimuthal contributions of
942 enstrophy during the interaction, pointing to a redistribution of vorticity due to the presence
943 of the bubble.

944 By employing advanced 3D diagnostics, this work addresses the challenge of capturing
945 the complex, transient, and non-linear phenomena that elude 2D measurements, provid-
946 ing valuable, high-fidelity data to address questions about the actual 3D evolution of
947 vorticity and enstrophy during bubble-vortex interactions. The detailed characterisation of
948 the bubble/particle-vortex interaction yields crucial insights into the physical mechanisms
949 governing the coupling between the phases. Future work could fruitfully extend this analysis
950 with the detailed temporal evolution of the bubble dynamics—directly accessible from
951 the reconstruction data—aiming to clarify the fundamental mechanisms driving bubble
952 deformation and eventual breakup. Furthermore, we plan to complement the flow analysis
953 with data assimilation techniques, which will provide further resolution of the flow around the
954 bubble, a key step to estimate accurately the turbulent stresses and the pressure field during
955 the interaction process. These findings are essential for advancing physics-based models of
956 bubble breakup and turbulence modulation in complex bubbly flows.

957 **Supplementary data.** Supplementary movies are available at <https://doi.org/...>

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Figure 20: Perspective views of the calibration target from each camera.

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969 **Data availability statement.** The data that support the findings of this study are available upon reasonable
 970 request

971 Appendix A. Calibration procedure

972 A bi-planar two-faces calibration target from LaVision GmbH (Ref. No. 204-15) was
 973 immersed in the tank filled with water and placed opposite the front cameras. To cover
 974 the full volume of interest, the target was recorded in multiple positions (11 positions 10
 975 mm apart), assuring that its centre could still be seen from all the cameras (see figure 20).
 976 Given the complex camera arrangement, the lateral view of the calibration plate was only
 977 partial, so the lateral images were masked to guarantee that only the plate pattern was taken
 978 into account for the calibration. The pattern was manually interpreted with DaVis software,
 979 which then computed the 3D calibration function. This function consisted of a polynomial
 980 fit which provided a mapping from the camera sensor coordinates to the real-world ones
 981 for each camera, while considering potential refraction due to the light crossing different
 982 media in between (Pavlov *et al.* 2021). The calibration was corrected for every experimental
 983 set by performing a volumetric self-calibration of uncorrelated images of the particles,
 984 which iteratively modifies the original calibration function to reduce disparities accounting
 985 for many sources of errors, such as optical distortions, vibrations, thermal expansions, or
 986 experimental uncertainties on the calibration process (Wieneke 2008, 2018). The resulting
 987 optical transfer function (OTF) considers the shape of each detected particle, which enables
 988 easier identification of such a particle in the successive images, reducing the probability of
 989 ghost particles (Schanz *et al.* 2012). The particle images were pre-processed to condition the
 990 particle intensity and to reduce noise, so that the Shake-The-Box (STB) technique (Schanz
 991 *et al.* 2016) may be employed to capture the evolution of the flow.

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